

Dongfang Special Entangled Solution of Schrödinger Hydrogen Equation

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Abstract: The textbook solutions of Schrödinger equations are usually represented as the combination of multiple special function symbols, resulting in a large number of missing exact solutions not being discovered. Taking the Schrödinger wave function of a hydrogen atom as an example, regressing to the analytical expression that can be extended and programmed for testing, two types of special entangled wave functions that have not been described by established theories have been discovered. Specifically, when the magnetic quantum number is 0, the traditional Schrödinger wave function degenerates into a binary function about radial variables r and angle θ without angles ϕ . The conclusion of this reasoning process, which seems very rigorous in the traditional sense, is actually extremely untrue. The Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms has two types of special entangled solutions with magnetic quantum numbers of 0, and the sine and cosine functions of angle ϕ are included in it, implying that there are other unknown wave functions that satisfy the Schrödinger equation and even affect the energy eigenvalue formula. The three-dimensional function image of the special entangled solution of the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation is further drawn. The results show intuitively and clearly that there is no one-to-one correspondence between the zero or extreme point of the modulus function of the ternary function and that of the square of the modulus function of the ternary function. It is concluded that the definition of the square of the wave function modulus as the probability density function lacks causality, and it is an urgent problem to derive the probability density function according to the basic principle.

Keywords: Hydrogen atom, Schrödinger equation, special entangled spherical harmonic function, Schrödinger wave function, special entangled wave function, probability density function.

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1 Introduction

The mathematical processes of quantum mechanics seem perfect enough. However, new research has found that the set of known eigensolutions of certain partial differential equations, such as spherical harmonic partial differential equations, is not the complete solution set of the equation, but one of the subsets. Early partial differential equation theory tended to obtain exact solutions to equations, while early quantum mechanics tended to obtain energy eigenvalues through exact solutions to wave equations, leading to the neglect of the integrity of the solution set of partial differential equations in both mathematics and physics. Of course, now we urgently need to understand the complete solution sets of various wave equations in order to present the quantum mechanical landscape of truly perfect mathematical processes.

The local exact solution of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms contains energy eigenvalue that are astonishingly consistent with the Bohr hydrogen atom energy formula. This unexpected gain promoted the birth of quantum mechanics and its rapid promotion and chain development, which in turn gave rise to a large number of financially successful large-scale quantum experimental projects. Experimental projects fed back beautification projects, forcing strict ideological unity. The argument that the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms perfectly reveals the law of low-speed microscopic motion is therefore, deeply ingrained in people's minds. The Bohr hydrogen atom theory based on the assumption of angular momentum quantization explains the spectral structure of hydrogen atoms. The Schrödinger equation itself is a hypothesis, but it constructs a theoretical framework for describing microscopic phenomena with partial differential equations satisfied by wave functions of being not truly clear in meaning, thus becoming the fundamental equation of quantum mechanics.

The spherical harmonic partial differential equation obtained by decomposing the Schrödinger equation in spherical coordinates is completely consistent with the angular momentum square operator equation, which hides various forms of missing solutions. Therefore, as a second-order partial differential equation, the traditional exact solution of the time-dependent stationary Schrödinger equation is only a subset of the equation's intrinsic solution set. The Schrödinger equation has other sets of intrinsic solutions that satisfy boundary conditions. The discovery of a large number of missing exact solutions to wave equations will inject new vitality into quantum mechanics.

To briefly illustrate the phenomenon of missing solutions to those wave equations, this paper first introduces two types of zero magnetic quantum number special entangled solutions for the Schrodinger equation of hydrogen atoms that have not been described by established theories. The complete set of special entangled function general solution containing local meanings of known solutions is given, indicating that the boundedness and normalization conditions of the wave function are not sufficient to determine the special solution. Although the energy eigenvalues of hydrogen atoms are not currently affected by special entanglement solutions, except for the ground state case, the three-dimensional contour images clearly indicate that the spatial distribution of the square of the Schrödinger wave function modulus defined as a probability density function does not correspond one-to-one with the spatial distribution of the wave function modulus, and the experimental observability of the statistical significance of the wave function is broken.

2 The traditional analytical solution of Schrödinger hydrogen equation

Usually, Z represents the nuclear charge of a hydrogen like atom; \hbar represents the reduced Planck constant defined by the so-called Planck constant h , α represents the fine-structure constant, and c represents the speed of light in the vacuum. Marking $A = Z\alpha$, the potential energy of a hydrogen like atomic system in a spherical coordinate system can be expressed in the following

simple form,

$$U(r) = -\frac{A\hbar c}{r} \tag{2.1}$$

The charge e of electrons is included in the fine-structure constant.

It should be pointed out that theoretically, the so-called fine structure constant α or Planck constant h is not a true constant. α and h should be referred to as fine structure parameters and Planck parameters, respectively. It is strongly recommended that experimental physicists accurately determine the distribution table of fine structural parameters α or Planck parameter h , as this is a significant scientific experiment that subverts traditional limiting thinking. But for hydrogen atoms, the product αh is a constant. Therefore, expression (2.1) is not affected by future experimental conclusions.

There are too many conjectures or hypotheses about the principles of quantum mechanics. A correct conjecture or assumption necessarily implies a strict causal relationship, which may not actually be complex, but may not be noticed. The experimental data is often corrected as needed, and there are actually many different or even completely opposite explanations for the conclusions. Therefore, rigorous logic is the preferred choice for scientific theory. In order to maintain logical rigor and conciseness, we summarize the characteristic solution theory of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen like atoms as the following definite solution problem.

Problem: Assuming the reduced mass of a hydrogen like atom is μ , the exact solution of the Schrödinger equation that satisfies the boundedness and normalization conditions of the wave function constitutes the definite solution problem

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu}\nabla^2\psi - \frac{A\hbar c}{r}\psi = E\psi \\ \psi(r \rightarrow \infty) = 0, \quad \psi(0 \leq r, 0 \leq \theta \leq \pi, 0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi) \neq \pm\infty \\ \psi(r, \theta + 2\pi, \varphi + 2\pi) = \psi(r, \theta, \varphi) \\ \int_{r=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_{\theta=0}^{\pi} \left[\int_{\varphi=0}^{2\pi} \psi(r, \theta, \varphi) \psi^*(r, \theta, \varphi) r^2 \sin\theta d\varphi \right] d\theta \right\} dr = 1 \end{array} \right. \tag{2.2}$$

Where

$$\nabla^2\psi = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial\theta^2} + \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2\theta} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial\varphi^2} \right) \tag{2.3}$$

The definite solution problem is a concise and accurate concrete expression of the quantum mechanical principles of Schrödinger hydrogen atoms. The Schrödinger equation is usually decomposed into radial ordinary differential equations and angular differential equations using the method of separating variables. The angular differential equation is a spherical harmonic partial differential equation. The solution of the radial ordinary differential equation is represented by the Laguerre function, and the solution of the spherical harmonic partial differential equation is represented by the associated Legendre function. The textbook solution to the Schrödinger equation for a hydrogen atom commonly uses abbreviations for these functions. Abbreviations may seem concise, but in reality, due to being too abstract, the question of whether the given solution is a complete set solution is completely ignored. The analytical form of the regression wave function makes the structure of the exact solution to the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms clear, which not only facilitates the verification of the solution, but also helps to discover missing solutions. Here, a lemma is used to represent the textbook solution of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms.

Lemma 1 (Traditional solution of Schrödinger equation): If the integer m , natural number l ,

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi_{6,2}^{(0)} &= a_{6,2} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^2 + 120r^2 \left(-\frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{1088640\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{15120\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{720\hbar} \right) \right] (1 - 3\cos^2\theta) \\
\psi_{6,3}^{(0)} &= b_{6,3} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^3 + 5040r^3 \left(\frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{3265920\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{60480\hbar} \right) \right] \left(\cos\theta - \frac{5\cos^3\theta}{3} \right) \\
\psi_{6,4}^{(0)} &= a_{6,4} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(r^4 - \frac{cA\mu r^5}{30\hbar} \right) \left(1 - 10\cos^2\theta + \frac{35\cos^4\theta}{3} \right) \\
\psi_{6,5}^{(0)} &= b_{6,5} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} r^5 \left(\cos\theta - \frac{14\cos^3\theta}{3} + \frac{21\cos^5\theta}{5} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

3.2 The first type of special entangled wave function for hydrogen

Replacing $\cos\theta$ with $\sin\phi\sin\theta$ in the traditional wave function (3.1) of the Schrödinger equation for zero magnetic quantum numbers of hydrogen atoms yields a new series of wave functions that satisfy the Schrödinger equation, known as the first kind of special entangled wave function for hydrogen atoms.

Theorem 1 (The first kind of special bounded entangled wave function): If the natural number l and the positive integer n satisfy the condition $l < n$, then the first kind of special bounded entangled wave function

$$\xi_{n,l}^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \begin{cases} \left\{ \underbrace{\left[e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{n\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{n\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right]}_{l=0,2,4,\dots} \right. \\ \left. \times c_{n,l}^{(0)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) (\sin\varphi\sin\theta)^{2j} \right\}; \\ \left\{ \underbrace{\left[e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{n\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{n\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right]}_{l=1,3,5,\dots} \right. \\ \left. \times d_{n,l}^{(0)} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) (\sin\varphi\sin\theta)^{2j+1} \right\} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

with an undetermined coefficient $c_{n,l}$ or $d_{n,l}$ satisfies the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2\theta} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar r} + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \xi = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

the energy eigenvalue in the equation is

$$E = -\frac{\mu A^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

The proof of Theorem 1 is divided into two parts: the radial wave function satisfies the radial Schrödinger equation and the angular wave function satisfies the spherical harmonic partial differential equation. The radial wave function is a well-known weighted Laguerre function and does not require further proof. The proof that the angular entanglement function satisfies the spherical harmonic equation is just a simple but lengthy calculation, as seen in the article entitled special entanglement spherical harmonic function^[1], which is omitted here. Table 3.2 lists the first kind of special entanglement solutions for the Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atoms calculated based on (3.3), taking $n-l = 0, 1, \dots, 10$, respectively. It can be verified that all wave functions in the

table satisfy the stationary Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms as stated in the theorem.

Table 3.2 Partial first type special entanglement solutions for zero magnetic quantum numbers in the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{6,0}^{(0)} &= c_{6,0} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(1 - \frac{c^5 A^5 \mu^5 r^5}{174960\hbar^5} + \frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{1944\hbar^4} - \frac{5c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{324\hbar^3} + \frac{5c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{27\hbar^2} - \frac{5cA\mu r}{6\hbar} \right) \\ \xi_{6,1}^{(0)} &= d_{6,1} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r + 6r \left(\frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{408240\hbar^4} - \frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{4860\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{180\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{18\hbar} \right) \right] \sin \varphi \sin \theta \\ \xi_{6,2}^{(0)} &= c_{6,2} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^2 + 120r^2 \left(-\frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{1088640\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{15120\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{720\hbar} \right) \right] (1 - 3\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \\ \xi_{6,3}^{(0)} &= d_{6,3} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^3 + 5040r^3 \left(\frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{3265920\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{60480\hbar} \right) \right] \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5\sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta}{3} \right) \\ \xi_{6,4}^{(0)} &= c_{6,4} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(r^4 - \frac{cA\mu r^5}{30\hbar} \right) \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35\sin^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta}{3} \right) \\ \xi_{6,5}^{(0)} &= d_{6,5} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} r^5 \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{14\sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta}{3} + \frac{21\sin^5 \varphi \sin^5 \theta}{5} \right) \end{aligned}$$

3.3 The second type of special entangled wave function for hydrogen

In the traditional wave function (3.1) of the zero magnetic quantum number Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms, $\cos \theta$ is replaced with $\cos \phi \sin \theta$ to obtain a new series of wave functions that also satisfy the Schrödinger equation. The second kind of special entangled wave function called hydrogen atoms.

Theorem 2 (The second kind of special bounded entangled wave function) If the natural number l and the positive integer n satisfy the condition $l < n$, then the second kind of special bounded entangled wave function

$$\zeta_{n,l}^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \begin{cases} \left\{ e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{n\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta - n + l)}{\eta(\eta + 2l + 1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{n\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times f_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 2)(2k + l - 1)}{2k(2k - 1)} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \right\}; \\ l=0, 2, 4, \dots \\ \left\{ e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{n\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta - n + l)}{\eta(\eta + 2l + 1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{n\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times g_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 1)(2k + l)}{(2k + 1)2k} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \right\} \\ l=1, 3, 5, \dots \end{cases} \tag{3.5}$$

with an undetermined coefficient $f_{n,l}$ or $g_{n,l}$ satisfies the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar r} + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \zeta = 0 \tag{3.6}$$

the energy eigenvalue in the equation is

$$E = -\frac{\mu A^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

The proof process of Theorem 2 is the same as that of Theorem 1, which is omitted here. Table 3.3 lists the second kind of special entangled solutions of the Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom calculated by taking $n-l = 0, 1, \dots, 10$ in (3.5) respectively. It can be verified that all wave functions in the table satisfy the stationary Schrödinger equation of the hydrogen atom described in the theorem.

Table 3.3 Part of the second kind of special entangled solutions of the zero magnetic quantum number of the Schrödinger equation for the hydrogen atom

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta_{6,0}^{(0)} &= f_{6,0} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(1 - \frac{c^5 A^5 \mu^5 r^5}{174960\hbar^5} + \frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{1944\hbar^4} - \frac{5c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{324\hbar^3} + \frac{5c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{27\hbar^2} - \frac{5cA\mu r}{6\hbar} \right) \\
\zeta_{6,1}^{(0)} &= g_{6,1} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r + 6r \left(\frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{408240\hbar^4} - \frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{4860\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{180\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{18\hbar} \right) \right] \sin \theta \cos \varphi \\
\zeta_{6,2}^{(0)} &= f_{6,2} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^2 + 120r^2 \left(-\frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{1088640\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{15120\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{720\hbar} \right) \right] (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi) \\
\zeta_{6,3}^{(0)} &= g_{6,3} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^3 + 5040r^3 \left(\frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{3265920\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{60480\hbar} \right) \right] \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{5\sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi}{3} \right) \\
\zeta_{6,4}^{(0)} &= f_{6,4} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(r^4 - \frac{cA\mu r^5}{30\hbar} \right) \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{35\sin^4 \theta \cos^4 \varphi}{3} \right) \\
\zeta_{6,5}^{(0)} &= g_{6,5} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} r^5 \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{14\sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi}{3} + \frac{21\sin^5 \theta \cos^5 \varphi}{5} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

4 Three types of special wave functions and probability density diagrams

The dogmatic idea of quantum mechanics is that the Bohr hydrogen atom energy formula is an inevitable result of the Schrödinger equation satisfying the definite solution condition, which is considered an important symbol of the success of quantum mechanics. Therefore, the application of partial differential equations to quantum theory seems to have achieved new breakthroughs. However, partial differential equations conceal numerous mathematical principles that subvert scientific theories and have been overlooked. The application of partial differential equations in physics and other scientific theories may not necessarily conform to mathematical and scientific significance, and may even violate mathematical and scientific common sense. The concise conclusion is that mathematical and scientific theories seriously lack a correct understanding of partial differential equations. In the future, we will gradually introduce and explain in detail the answers to relevant questions. Here we first focus on the intrinsic physical meaning of the wave function. There is an inevitable causality that if the square of the modulus function of the wave function represents the probability density, then for a specific physical model, such as the hydrogen atom model, the probability density function should be derived by using the basic principles of mathematics and physics, and then it is proved that the probability density function satisfies the Schrödinger equation. In fact, if the probability density function with clear meaning is derived, it does not satisfy the Schrödinger equation. This is an unsolved mystery of quantum mechanics.

Born proposed a statistical interpretation of the wave function and was quickly accepted. The product of a pair of conjugate wave functions is defined as the probability density of particles appearing in space. This definition is unproven and unprovable. It may come from the extension of the characteristics of univariate oscillatory real functions. The modulus of one-dimensional wave function can represent the relative distribution of the quantity described by the oscillating function, but the calculus operation of the modulus of the wave function is inconvenient. From the absolute value of the one-variable oscillating real function to the square of the one-variable

oscillating real function, the extreme point and the zero point are unchanged, and have the characteristics of conformal transformation. Extending to the complex variable function, the product of a pair of conjugate univariate complex variable functions is the square of the modular function. From the modular function of the complex variable function to the square of the modular function, it also has the characteristics of conformal transformation, and the extreme point and zero point are unchanged. The unsolved problem implied in the logic that the abstract meaning is greater than the concrete meaning is that from the absolute value of the unary real function to the even power of the unary real function, or from the modulus function of the unary complex variable function to the even power of the modulus function of the unary complex variable function, there are the characteristics of conformal transformation. How to prove that the probability density is the product of the modulus function of the wave function rather than some other even power of the modulus function ?

However, for multivariate wave functions, from the absolute value of the function to the square of the function, or from the modulus function of the complex variable function to the square of the modulus function, there is no feature of conformal transformation, and the extreme points and zero points cannot remain unchanged. The special wave function of zero magnetic quantum number is a real function, which is very convenient to clarify the essence of the problem. Table 4.1 draws the contour lines of the modulus function and the square of the modulus function of the special wave function of three zero magnetic quantum numbers. The range is $\theta \in [0, \pi]$, $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, $r \in [0, 2\hbar/A\mu c]$ in the case of $l = 0$, $r \in [0, 25\hbar/A\mu c]$ in the case of $l > 0$. The blank areas in the figure indicate that the function values are relatively large and insignificant. It is found that only the modulus function of the radial one-dimensional wave function with orbital angle quantum number $l = 0$ is similar to the square of the modulus function, while the square of the three-dimensional wave function with $l > 0$ from the modulus function to the modulus function is distorted. This proves that defining the probability density as the square of the modulus function cannot prove whether it is scientific, and the definition itself is completely negated by the multivariate wave function.

Table 4.1 Three kinds of special bounded wave function modulus and three-dimensional contour of probability density for n = 6

l	$\psi_{6,l}^{(0)}$	$(\psi_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$	$\xi_{6,l}^{(0)}$	$(\xi_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$	$\zeta_{6,l}^{(0)}$	$(\zeta_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$
0						
1						
2						

l	$ \psi_{6,l}^{(0)} $	$(\psi_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$	$ \xi_{6,l}^{(0)} $	$(\xi_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$	$ \zeta_{6,l}^{(0)} $	$(\zeta_{6,l}^{(0)})^2$
3						
4						
5						

5 Integrated special entanglement Schrödinger wave function of hydrogen

Any multivariate function will inevitably satisfy many partial differential equations. As a solution to the Schrödinger equation of the second-order partial differential equation of a multivariate function, the square of the wave function's modulus is used to define probability density, an extremely abstract physical quantity. This definition does not have any causal relationship, but rather a construction that yields to specific expectations. It is necessary to determine the specific form of the wave function, but quantum mechanics cannot provide the initial conditions for second-order partial differential equations, and it is not enough to only assign bounded conditions to the wave equation. Therefore, the normalization condition is proposed. Proposing normalization conditions is quite creative. However, the normalization condition only applies to positively definite bounded functions and not to unbounded and oscillatory functions. Taking the square of the wave function modulus that satisfies the bounded condition of the function yields a positive definite function, which is the reason defining the probability density function. This definition, as we now know, does not satisfy the uniqueness theorem. The serious problem is that the bounded and normalized conditions of the wave function cannot actually determine the specific form of the wave function. The specific forms of wave functions given by established theories are not logical inferences that conform to the existence and uniqueness theorems, but rather cunning conclusions that force specific computational orders. Given the powerful logical power of proof by contradiction, here we discuss the integration of special entangled Schrödinger wave functions to specifically prove the above statement.

The linear combination of all special solutions satisfying the linear differential equation is the general solution of the linear differential equation. The general solutions of linear ordinary differential equations obtained by different methods are equivalent. The general solutions of a linear partial differential equation obtained by different methods are not necessarily equivalent, but are various local general solutions. The linear combination of all local general solutions is the complete set general solution of the linear partial differential equation. However, there is no basic principle that can explain how many local general solutions a linear partial differential equation has. The linear combination of multiple local general solutions of a linear partial differential equation may be only a subset of the complete set general solution. We summarize Lemma 2,

Theorem 1 and Theorem 2 to obtain the integrated special entanglement solution of the zero magnetic quantum number of the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation.

Theorem 3 (Integrated specially bounded entangled wave function): If any natural number l and positive integer n satisfy the condition $l < n$, then the integrated specially bounded entangled wave function

$$\Upsilon_{n,l}^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{\hbar}} \left(r^l + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta - n + l)}{\eta(\eta + 2l + 1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{l+\nu} \right) \\ \left[a_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 2)(2k + l - 1)}{2k(2k - 1)} \right) \cos^{2j}\theta \right. \\ \left. + c_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 2)(2k + l - 1)}{2k(2k - 1)} \right) (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \right. \\ \left. + f_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 2)(2k + l - 1)}{2k(2k - 1)} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \right] \end{array} \right\}; \tag{5.1}$$

$l=0, 2, 4, \dots$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} e^{-\frac{A\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta - n + l)}{\eta(\eta + 2l + 1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \\ \left[b_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 1)(2k + l)}{(2k + 1)2k} \right) \cos^{2j+1}\theta \right. \\ \left. + d_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 1)(2k + l)}{(2k + 1)2k} \right) (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \right. \\ \left. + g_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k - l - 1)(2k + l)}{(2k + 1)2k} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \right] \end{array} \right\}$$

$l=1, 3, 5, \dots$

with three undetermined coefficients $a_{n,l}$, $c_{n,l}$ and $f_{n,l}$ (or $b_{n,l}$, $d_{n,l}$ and $g_{n,l}$) satisfies the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar r} + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \Upsilon = 0 \tag{5.2}$$

the energy eigenvalue in the equation is

$$E = -\frac{\mu A^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

When the total quantum number $n = 6$, the orbital quantum numbers $l = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ are substituted into (5.1), or the wave functions with the same orbital quantum number in Table 3.1, Table 3.2 and Table 3.3 are added directly, and all the integrated special entangled wave functions with the total quantum number $n = 6$ and the magnetic quantum number zero are obtained. The results are listed in 5.1. It can be checked that these integrated special entangled wave functions satisfy the Schrödinger equation.

The integrated entangled special entangled wave function with zero magnetic quantum number has three undetermined constants. The complete wave function of this special case cannot be determined only by the normalization condition. In order to obtain a complete special entangled wave function, two definite conditions must be supplemented. In the past, the undetermined

coefficients of three kinds of special wave functions were determined by normalization conditions, and then linear combination was carried out. In fact, the integrated wave function proposed by this reversed logic still has three undetermined coefficients, and the specific form of the wave function cannot be determined by the normalization condition alone. The reversal of logic is extremely confusing. The integrated entangled special entangled wave function with zero magnetic quantum number shows that the Schrödinger wave function of hydrogen atom is uncertain in the established quantum mechanics framework.

Table 5.1 Partially integrated special entanglement solutions of zero magnetic quantum number for Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom

$$\begin{aligned}
\Upsilon_{6,0}^{(0)} &= \alpha_{6,0} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(1 - \frac{c^5 A^5 \mu^5 r^5}{174960\hbar^5} + \frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{1944\hbar^4} - \frac{5c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{324\hbar^3} + \frac{5c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{27\hbar^2} - \frac{5cA\mu r}{6\hbar} \right) \\
\Upsilon_{6,1}^{(0)} &= \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r + 6r \left(\frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{408240\hbar^4} - \frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{4860\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{180\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{18\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\quad \times \{ b_{6,1} \cos \theta + d_{6,1} \sin \varphi \sin \theta + g_{6,1} \sin \theta \cos \varphi \} \\
\Upsilon_{6,2}^{(0)} &= \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^2 + 120r^2 \left(-\frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{1088640\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{15120\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{720\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\quad \times \{ a_{6,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) + c_{6,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) + f_{6,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi) \} \\
\Upsilon_{6,3}^{(0)} &= \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^3 + 5040r^3 \left(\frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{3265920\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{60480\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\quad \times \left[\begin{aligned} &b_{6,3} \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \theta \right) + d_{6,3} \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \\ &+ g_{6,3} \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi \right) \end{aligned} \right] \\
\Upsilon_{6,4}^{(0)} &= e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(r^4 - \frac{cA\mu r^5}{30\hbar} \right) \left\{ \begin{aligned} &a_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \theta \right) \\ &+ c_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \\ &+ f_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \cos^4 \varphi \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
\Upsilon_{6,5}^{(0)} &= e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} r^5 \left\{ \begin{aligned} &b_{6,5} \left(\cos \theta - \frac{14}{3} \cos^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \cos^5 \theta \right) \\ &+ d_{6,5} \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \varphi \sin^5 \theta \right) \\ &+ g_{6,5} \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \theta \cos^5 \varphi \right) \end{aligned} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

The ultimate goal of wave equation theory is not to obtain energy eigenvalues. The fundamental purpose of solving the wave equation is to obtain the specific wave function that meets the definite solution conditions and give the wave function real meaning. To determine the specific integrated wave function of the Schrödinger hydrogen equation in the special case of zero magnetic quantum number, it is critical to supplement two appropriate definite conditions, but this is not easy. Table 5.2 draws the three-dimensional contour of the integrated special wave function of several different combinations of undetermined coefficients in the range of $\theta \in [0, \pi]$, $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, $r \in [0, 2\hbar/(cA\mu)]$ in the case of $l = 0$, and $r \in [0, 25\hbar/(cA\mu)]$ in the case of $l > 0$. The blank difference indicates that

the function value is relatively large. The three-dimensional contour intuitively shows that the distribution of the special integrated wave functions of different combinations of undetermined coefficients is different for the zero magnetic quantum number determined by any total quantum number n and orbital angular momentum quantum number l . Therefore, the urgent problem to be solved in the wave equation theory of quantum mechanics is to propose suitable and sufficient conditions for the definite solution. In the absence of sufficient and reasonable definite conditions, the specific form of the wave function cannot be determined, and the development results of the wave equation theory of quantum mechanics imply greater uncertainty.

Tab. 5.2 Three-dimensional contour lines of partially integrated special wave functions for Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom

$\Upsilon_{n,l}^{(0)}$	$(a_{n,l}, c_{n,l}, f_{n,l}) = (b_{n,l}, d_{n,l}, g_{n,l})$					
	(1, 1, 0)	(0, 1, 1)	(1, 0, 1)	(1, 1, 1)	(1, 5, 10)	(10, 5, 1)
$\Upsilon_{6,0}^{(0)}$						
$\Upsilon_{6,1}^{(0)}$						
$\Upsilon_{6,2}^{(0)}$						
$\Upsilon_{6,3}^{(0)}$						
$\Upsilon_{6,4}^{(0)}$						
$\Upsilon_{6,5}^{(0)}$						

6 Complete set of special entangled Schrödinger wave functions for hydrogen

The integrated special entangled wave function of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms with zero magnetic quantum numbers listed earlier belongs to the general form of the sub solution set of the Schrödinger equation. The subset of solutions cannot be summed up for the total quantum number n , but it can be summed up for all orbital angular quantum numbers l that satisfy the condition $l < n$. The resulting wave function belongs to the special wave function of the complete set with local significance. The complete set special wave function has $3n - 2$ undetermined coefficients, and relying solely on the normalization condition can obviously only determine the ground state wave function with $n = 1$. However, with the increase of the main quantum number, the required solution condition increases nearly threefold. This decisive factor has been overlooked in the past, leading to a biased development of the theory. The complete set of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms and the expression for the special wave function are as follows.

Theorem 4 (Complete set special bounded entangled wave function) Let any natural number l and positive integer n satisfy the condition $l < n$, then the complete set special bounded entangled wave function

$$\begin{aligned}
\Upsilon_n^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \Upsilon_{n,l}^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) \\
&= \sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[e^{-\frac{\Delta\mu cr}{\hbar}} \left(r^l + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{l+\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \left[\begin{array}{l} a_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) \cos^{2j}\theta \\ + c_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) (\sin\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j} \\ + f_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) (\cos\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j} \end{array} \right] \right\} \\
&\quad \left. \begin{array}{l} l=0, 2, 4, \dots \\ + \\ \left[e^{-\frac{\Delta\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \left[\begin{array}{l} b_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) \cos^{2j+1}\theta \\ + d_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) (\sin\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j+1} \\ + g_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) (\cos\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j+1} \end{array} \right] \right\} \\
&\quad \left. \begin{array}{l} l=1, 3, 5, \dots \end{array} \right\} \quad (6.1)
\end{aligned}$$

with $3n - 2$ independent undetermined coefficients $a_{n,l}$, $c_{n,l}$ and $f_{n,l}$ (or $b_{n,l}$, $d_{n,l}$ and $g_{n,l}$) satisfies the stationary Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{\Upsilon} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{2A\mu c}{\hbar} r + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} r^2 + \frac{1}{\Upsilon} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2\theta} \frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \phi^2} \right) = 0 \quad (6.2)$$

the energy eigenvalue in the equation is

$$E = -\frac{\mu A^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

In the special case of only zero magnetic quantum number, there are $3n$ undetermined coefficients in the special general solution form of the complete set of the Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom. However, the three terms of $l = 0$ are combined into one item, and the undetermined coefficient is equivalent to $a_{n,0} + c_{n,0} + f_{n,0} = \beta_{n,0}$. In fact, there are $3n - 2$ independent undetermined constants. In addition to the normalization conditions, $3n - 3$ definite conditions are needed to determine the specific form of the wave function. The principal quantum number n can be a non-negative arbitrary integer, which means that the specific wave function cannot be determined according to the special general solution of the complete set of the Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom. The normalized wave function of hydrogen atom given by quantum mechanics is an illusion rather than an inevitable inference, and its process does not conform to mathematical principles. Using the wave function of uncertain specific form to obtain the determined energy eigenvalue, or using the theory of uncertainty of credibility to deduce the conclusion of expectation, there is a coincidence and therefore it is extremely mysterious.

There are some implicit conditions in modern physics that determine the development of theory. Some of these conditions are not based on the promotion of theoretical perfection, but only to avoid the orientation of inevitable causality. Extreme expectations that do not conform to the facts are often described as the inevitable laws of nature. Using the square of the wave function modulus to define the probability density of particles appearing in space is only an example.

The problem of the solution set of the Schrödinger equation, which belongs to the second-order partial differential equation, has not been correctly handled in modern physics. The basic principle of the solution of the differential equation is that the linear combination of all the solutions satisfying the linear differential constitutes the general solution of the linear differential equation, and the specific solution of the linear differential equation is a special function that can satisfy the definite solution condition. Partial differential equations lead to different kinds of local general solutions because of different methods. The linear system of these local general solutions constitutes a wider range of general solutions of partial differential equations. The local general solution is a sub-solution set. The simpler the coefficients of linear partial differential equations are, the more the sub solution sets are. The Laplace equation is the simplest linear partial differential equation. At present, it seems that it is impossible to give a conclusion on how many sub-solution sets it has. It is too early to give a conclusion about how many sub-solution sets Schrödinger equation has. The special entanglement solution set of the Schrödinger equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers is sufficient to demonstrate that the credibility of established scientific theories described by partial differential equations is very low.

7 The uncertainty of normalized Schrödinger wave functions

The above Equation (6.1) gives the zero magnetic quantum number general solution of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atom or hydrogen-like atom. Using the normalization condition, only the ground state solution can be determined, so as to obtain the ground state wave function, and any excited state wave function can not be determined. Normalization conditions of the special bounded entangled wave function of the Schrödinger complete set of hydrogen atoms are usually written as follows,

$$\int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \Upsilon_n^{(0)}(r, \theta, \phi) d\phi \right) \sin \theta d\theta \right] r^2 dr = \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{l=0}^5 \Upsilon_{n,l}^{(0)}(r, \theta, \phi) d\phi \right) \sin \theta d\theta \right] r^2 dr = 1 \quad (7.1)$$

The linear combination of the six integrated special wave functions in Table 5.1 is the calculation result of $n = 6$ in (5.1). In the form, this gives the complete set entangled wave function of the Schrödinger theory of the hydrogen atom with 16 undetermined coefficients and zero magnetic quantum numbers, which is represented by the symbol $\Upsilon_6^{(0)} = \sum_{l=0}^5 \Upsilon_{6,l}^{(0)}$. The result is,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Upsilon_6^{(0)} &= \sum_{l=0}^5 \Upsilon_{6,l}^{(0)} = \\
&\alpha_{6,0} e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(1 - \frac{c^5 A^5 \mu^5 r^5}{174960\hbar^5} + \frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{1944\hbar^4} - \frac{5c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{324\hbar^3} + \frac{5c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{27\hbar^2} - \frac{5cA\mu r}{6\hbar} \right) \\
&+ \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r + 6r \left(\frac{c^4 A^4 \mu^4 r^4}{408240\hbar^4} - \frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{4860\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{180\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{18\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\times \left\{ b_{6,1} \cos \theta + d_{6,1} \sin \varphi \sin \theta + g_{6,1} \sin \theta \cos \varphi \right\} \\
&+ \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^2 + 120r^2 \left(-\frac{c^3 A^3 \mu^3 r^3}{1088640\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{15120\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{720\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\times \left\{ a_{6,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) + c_{6,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) + f_{6,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi) \right\} \\
&+ \left\{ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left[r^3 + 5040r^3 \left(\frac{c^2 A^2 \mu^2 r^2}{3265920\hbar^2} - \frac{cA\mu r}{60480\hbar} \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\times \left\{ \left[b_{6,3} \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \theta \right) + d_{6,3} \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \right] \right\} \\
&\times \left\{ \left[+g_{6,3} \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi \right) \right] \right\} \\
&+ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} \left(r^4 - \frac{cA\mu r^5}{30\hbar} \right) \left\{ \begin{aligned} &a_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \theta \right) \\ &+ c_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \\ &+ f_{6,4} \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \cos^4 \varphi \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
&+ e^{-\frac{cA\mu r}{6\hbar}} r^5 \left\{ \begin{aligned} &b_{6,5} \left(\cos \theta - \frac{14}{3} \cos^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \cos^5 \theta \right) \\ &+ d_{6,5} \left(\sin \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \varphi \sin^5 \theta \right) \\ &+ g_{6,5} \left(\sin \theta \cos \varphi - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \theta \cos^3 \varphi + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \theta \cos^5 \varphi \right) \end{aligned} \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{7.2}$$

This integrated special entangled wave function is a bounded function, but it has 16 undetermined coefficients and its specific form cannot be determined.

The logic of established quantum mechanics theory is to force a calculation sequence to normalize the function terms of each independent coefficient, determine each independent coefficient, and then integrate them, adding a new undetermined coefficient before each term, and focusing on describing the discrete wave functions of the independent coefficients. The calculation process does not conform to the basic principle of determining specific solutions from general solutions of differential equations. In fact, it was not possible to obtain a complete integrated wave function. However, the very cunning description hides serious logical issues.

If the wave function (7.2) is substituted into the so-called normalization condition (7.1), the

calculation result is a quadratic equation with 16 undetermined coefficients,

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &= \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \Upsilon_6^{(0)} d\varphi \right) \sin \theta d\theta \right] r^2 dr = \int_0^\infty \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \sum_{l=0}^5 \Upsilon_{6,l}^{(0)} d\varphi \right) \sin \theta d\theta \right] r^2 dr \\
 &= \frac{216\pi\hbar^3}{35c^{13}A^{13}\mu^{13}} \left\{ \begin{aligned}
 &35c^{10}A^{10}\mu^{10}a_{6,0}^2 + 29160c^6A^6\mu^6\hbar^4a_{6,2}^2 + 39504568320c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8a_{6,4}^2 \\
 &+ 108c^8A^8\mu^8\hbar^2b_{6,1}^2 + 1360800c^4A^4\mu^4\hbar^6b_{6,3}^2 + 12799480135680\hbar^{10}b_{6,5}^2 \\
 &+ 35c^{10}A^{10}\mu^{10}c_{6,0}^2 + 29160c^6A^6\mu^6\hbar^4c_{6,2}^2 + 29628426240c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8a_{6,4}c_{6,4} \\
 &+ 39504568320c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8c_{6,4}^2 + 108c^8A^8\mu^8\hbar^2d_{6,1}^2 + 1360800c^4A^4\mu^4\hbar^6d_{6,3}^2 \\
 &+ 12799480135680\hbar^{10}d_{6,5}^2 + 70c^{10}A^{10}\mu^{10}c_{6,0}f_{6,0} + 35c^{10}A^{10}\mu^{10}f_{6,0}^2 \\
 &+ 70c^{10}A^{10}\mu^{10}a_{6,0}(c_{6,0} + f_{6,0}) - 29160c^6A^6\mu^6\hbar^4c_{6,2}f_{6,2} + 29160c^6A^6\mu^6\hbar^4f_{6,2}^2 \\
 &- 29160c^6A^6\mu^6\hbar^4a_{6,2}(c_{6,2} + f_{6,2}) + 29628426240c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8a_{6,4}f_{6,4} \\
 &+ 29628426240c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8c_{6,4}f_{6,4} + 39504568320c^2A^2\mu^2\hbar^8f_{6,4}^2 \\
 &+ 108c^8A^8\mu^8\hbar^2g_{6,1}^2 + 1360800c^4A^4\mu^4\hbar^6g_{6,3}^2 + 12799480135680\hbar^{10}g_{6,5}^2
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{7.3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, when $n = 6, 15$ definite conditions are needed to determine the total 16 undetermined coefficients of the special entanglement wave function of the Schrödinger equation, so as to determine the specific special entanglement solution of the Schrödinger equation corresponding to the $n = 6$ energy level.

In the field of quantum mechanics, it is impossible to provide the other 15 definite solution conditions for determining the specific form of the wave function beyond the traditional normalization conditions. This is only a special case where the magnetic quantum number is zero. The Schrödinger wave function of hydrogen atoms can have many undetermined coefficients. Perhaps the uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics can have a more basic explanation, but the inherent uncertainty of Schrödinger wave functions in quantum mechanics cannot be solved. Normalization, as the only condition for determining bounded wave functions, was misunderstood, but historically it has been technically described perfectly. Human intelligence can always write theories by reversing right and wrong, just like applying normalization conditions to local general solutions of differential equations and then linearly combining them to give pseudo complete wave functions. However, the irreversible conclusion is that the normalization condition cannot be used to determine the non-ground state solution of the Schrödinger equation.

8 Comments

The traditional solution of the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation expressed by the product of the weighted Laguerre function and the traditional spherical harmonic function is incomplete. The traditional spherical harmonic function is a direct product function. It has been proved that there are two kinds of special entangled spherical harmonic functions even if the magnetic quantum number is zero. The linear combination of three kinds of special spherical harmonic functions constitutes the complete set special entangled function solution of the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation as a second-order partial differential equation, which is the Schrödinger complete set special entangled wave function of the hydrogen atom. The undetermined coefficients increase with the increase of the main quantum number, and there are a total of undetermined coefficients which cannot be determined by normalization conditions. There is no definite excited state solution for the rigorous mathematical definite solution problem of the Schrödinger equation of the hydrogen atom. The existence of entangled wave function proves that the mathematical

deduction of Schrödinger equation theory in quantum mechanics is incomplete.

The meaning of wave function touches the mathematical essence of quantum mechanics. The statistical significance of the wave function satisfying Schrödinger is generally accepted. However, in the past, based on the understanding of one-dimensional oscillatory functions such as harmonic functions, the square of the modulus function of the wave function was used to represent the probability density of the particle in space, which was completely negated by the multivariate wave function. From the module of one-dimensional wave function to the square of the module of one-dimensional wave function, it has the characteristics of conformal transformation, and the zero point and the extreme point are unchanged. However, from the module of the multivariate oscillation function to the square of the module of the multivariate oscillation function, the shape will be distorted. The probability density defined by the square of the modulus of the wave function is only applicable to the univariate wave function but not to the multivariate wave function. The solution of the Schrödinger equation of hydrogen atom is a linear combination of multivariate functions. The mystery of quantum mechanics is actually derived from the lack of basic mathematical knowledge and the excessive whitewash of deviating from the theme. The undetermined coefficients of the wave function are determined by the normalization condition, and the so-called probability density is expressed by the even power of the modulus of the wave function. All of these can not be proved to be the inevitable causality in nature, but it is fully proved that the results are uncertain and abnormal.

The conclusion of incomplete mathematical deduction is described as a universal law of nature, and the credibility of its experimental test results is very low. The usual experimental test of quantum mechanics is not intrinsically related to the probability density. Based on the physical conclusions of mathematical reasoning, the prerequisite for experimental testing is that the mathematical reasoning process must be reliable. The conclusions of some false inferences, subjective choices, and false calculations are often claimed to be confirmed by experiments. This is only a different interpretation of the observed data, and many observed data have enough different interpretations. The engineering of experimental verification of the expected conclusion must be based on correct and complete logical inference. There are many mathematical and conceptual problems to be solved in quantum mechanics. Although the development of quantum mechanics has bypassed these decisive problems, more and more confusion has arisen, which is the fundamental reason why the mathematical nature of quantum mechanics is not known. Only by solving enough basic problems that must be solved can quantum theory make a real breakthrough.

The Schrödinger equation theory of hydrogen atoms relies on mathematical reasoning. The physical theory based on mathematical reasoning cannot be separated from the constraints of the basic principles of mathematics and become an independent kingdom of singular logic. Perhaps we should admit a fact that only mathematicians participate in the demonstration, test, criticism and revision from beginning to end can we ensure the correctness, integrity and reliability of the establishment and development of physical theory.^[1]

References

- [1] Dongfang, X. D. [Dongfang Special Entangled Spherical Harmonic Functions](#). *Mathematics & Nature* 3, 202302 (2023).

Notes: All breakthrough new conclusions that cannot be fully expressed using past methods are described in the form of theorems, and these theorems and various new wave functions of the listed hydrogen atom Schrödinger theory have passed the computational tests of Wolfram Mathematica. For lengthy equations, formatting errors may occur during the process of writing Mathematica code. The equations need to be split into several parts and processed separately, and then combined to perform operations.

• **PS1: Why do contemporary breakthrough papers choose to be published in self media journals?**

This groundbreaking paper based on Dongfang Special Entangled Spherical Harmonic Functions was written within a week, aiming to reveal the serious confidence issues hidden in quantum mechanics and promote significant changes in scientific theory.

Before writing this paper, Nature Physics had sent a solicitation letter to the author, mainly inquiring about the author's recent research status, the title and abstract of the paper the author plans to submit to Nature Physics, and the estimated time required for the author to complete the research project. However, based on the fact that breakthrough papers submitted to Nature Physics in the past were all rejected, the author infers that Nature Physics is not genuinely soliciting submissions from the author, but is tentatively attempting to steal the core scientific principles needed to create a new Newtonian era and achieve the plan of revitalizing the country through science. The author did not reply to this solicitation letter and deleted it as spam.

After careful consideration, the author decided to submit the new important paper to Nature Physics for the last time, both to confirm his personal views on Nature and to respond to readers' doubts about the author's choice of publication method. The article submission number is [NPHYS-2024-06-01859](#). In the submitted version, the author removed important experimental suggestions written after the first equation. The reason for doing so is out of scientific belief and responsibility. The Nature journal has an absolute advantage in enticing the world to submit major breakthrough research results in a timely manner due to its enormous influence. Editors can efficiently assist domestic scientists in plagiarizing breakthrough discoveries that have changed the scientific world. Although the Nature team and its complex members, with their current level of scientific theory, do not have the ability to perfect partial differential equation theory and discover the fundamental principles of unified macroscopic and microscopic quantum theory after plagiarizing special entanglement function theory, if they shift their focus to plagiarizing breakthrough experimental ideas, profound misunderstandings may occur, leading science in a new wrong direction once again.

The author agreed to share this paper on [Research Square](#) when submitting it to Nature Physics. After 17 days of detailed dissection by numerous personnel, the editor of Nature Physics informed the author that their decision was not to send the paper for external review. This is expected.

Readers should be aware of the reality of the scientific world. On the one hand, because scientific theories play a crucial role in the field of ideology, scientific research in some countries is actually tied to political tasks. On the one hand, due to the enormous benefits of scientific research, some individuals who originally lacked the ability to conduct scientific research actively infiltrate the editorial and peer review teams of renowned academic journals, often plagiarizing and selling breakthrough submissions to maximize their personal interests. In the field of science, it usually takes a hundred or even hundreds of years for a few pioneering researchers to emerge. If you are a pioneering researcher, you will inevitably face numerous despicable opponents everywhere, so never expect your breakthrough research results to be accepted by reputable academic journals such as Nature. Instead, you should consider how to publicly disclose your research results and effectively do anti-theft and anti murder work, ensuring that great discoveries are not contaminated by ignorant and unethical editors or peer reviewers, and ensuring that readers with independent research capabilities are timely informed of new discoveries and develop theories correctly.

By reading numerous groundbreaking papers by authors, future pioneering researchers can also experience unique writing techniques that deter scientific thieves. However, there will always be just scientists in the world, which is the fundamental guarantee for the continuous progress of human civilization.

• PS2: Decision on Nature Physics manuscript NPHYS-2024-06-01859

Dear Professor Dongfang,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript entitled “Dongfang Special Entangled Solution of Schrödinger Hydrogen Equation” to Nature Physics. Please accept our apologies for the delay in reaching a decision on your manuscript. This delay is all the more regrettable as I’m sorry to say that we are unable to offer to publish it.

Owing to the fact that we receive more papers than we can publish, we decline a substantial proportion of manuscripts without sending them to reviewers, so that they may be sent elsewhere without delay. These decisions are made by the editorial staff, taking into account the probable appeal of the work to a broader physics community, as well as the likelihood that it would seem of great topical interest to those working in related areas of physics.

In the present case, we appreciate the specialist interest likely to be generated by your work. I regret, however, that we are unable to conclude that the paper in itself provides the sort of clear advance in scientific understanding that would be likely to excite the immediate interest of a diverse physics readership. We therefore feel that the present paper would find a more appropriate audience in a journal that publishes more specialised research.

I am sorry that we cannot respond more positively, and I hope that you will understand that our decision in no way reflects any doubts about the quality of the work reported. The unfortunate fact is that we receive many more papers than we can undertake to publish, and we must attempt to select those that will be of the greatest interest to a wide audience. I hope that you will rapidly receive a more favourable response elsewhere.

Yours sincerely,

Senior Editor

Nature Physics

• PS3: Important update regarding your manuscript

Dear Dr. XD Dongfang,

Although your manuscript “Dongfang Special Entangled Solution of Schrödinger Hydrogen Equation” is no longer undergoing peer review at Nature Physics, you can still use your Research Square Dashboard to improve your manuscript.

Post a preprint

You can still benefit from community feedback by sharing your manuscript publicly. If you would like to share your manuscript as a preprint, you can do that from the peer review timeline tab in your dashboard by clicking “Post My Preprint.”

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RSID: rs-4558194

† Based on past experiences, it is inferred that the hypocritical behavior of Research Square of Nature to rate actively the author’s language quality may be aimed at stealing the Word version of the paper to plagiarize those complex equations more quickly.